

Major, trace and rare earth element concentrations in NIST Standard Reference Material® 1646a analyzed by ALS Global using Method ME-MS61r

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Introduction

Reference materials, such as NIST Standard Reference Material® 1646a, are frequently used to monitor the accuracy of geochemical analyses. This specific material (1646a) is an estuarine sediment powder, and so may be used as a reference standard when analyzing powdered mud-rich sediments and sedimentary rocks. As with all [NIST Standard Reference Materials®](#), certain elements are certified to have known concentrations based on multiple analyses by instrumental neutron activation analysis (INAA), while other elements have reported values that are not certified (May & Rumble, 2004). This certification does not include many of the trace and rare earth elements (REE) that are frequently used by geochemists, for example in sediment provenance studies. However, Cao et al. (2017) published their results for this standard using both INAA and acid digestions followed by ICP analysis.

Data included in this report were collected while NIST Standard Reference Material® 1646a was being used as a reference standard for several different geochemical studies of sediments and sedimentary rocks, most of which focused on geochemical interpretations of sediment provenance (Alexander, 2022; Alexander et al., 2018, 2022, 2023, 2025)

This technical note compares the results obtained from ALS Global Method ME-MS61r with the certified and previously published results for NIST Standard Reference Material® 1646a, and aims to assess the validity of this method for geochemical research. The results are presented as major, trace and rare earth elements, and focus on elements used in geochemical studies of sediment provenance (e.g. Roser and Korsch 1988; Totten et al. 2000; Cullers 2002; Cho and Ohta 2022). This report should also serve as a reference for other studies using this material as a standard.

Method

Nine dried sub-samples of NIST Standard Reference Material® 1646a were sent to ALS Global on seven separate occasions between November 2016 and December 2023. All were analyzed using Method ME-MS61r, which uses a four acid digestion (ALS Global, 2025). The sample (0.25 g) is digested using hydrofluoric, perchloric, nitric and hydrochloric acids, and dilute hydrochloric acid is added to the residue. This is then analyzed using ICP-AES and ICP-MS for major, trace and rare earth elements, with the results being corrected for spectral interelement interferences (ALS Global, 2025).

The results from the nine ALS Global Method ME-MS63r analyses were compiled to calculate the mean and standard deviation (SD). These were then compared to the NIST certified and reported values (May & Rumble, 2004) and measured values from Cao et al. (2017). Where available, the Cao et al. (2017) values from an acid digestion, followed by ICP-AES and ICP-MS analysis are used in preference to those obtained by INAA, as this is most like ALS Global Method ME-MS61r. Comparisons are made between the mean values measured and those reported, and comments on how well the data agree refer to the SD of the measured mean values, not the errors and standard deviations of the reported values.

Results

Major elements

The mean concentrations of Fe, K, Mg, Mn, and Na are all within 1 SD of the certified values (Table 1). The mean concentration of Al is within 2 SD of the certified value, but is identical to the value reported by Cao et al. (2017). The mean concentrations of Ca and Ti are just outside 2 SD from the certified values, with Ca being higher than the certified concentration and Ti being lower. The mean concentration for Ca is closer (within 2 SD) to the result of Cao et al. (2017), which is also higher than the certified value. Ti is potentially present in minerals that may not be completely dissolved in the acid digestion (Totland et al., 1992), and could result in the measured mean being lower than the certified value determined by INAA. However, the higher reported concentration of Cao et al. (2017) would suggest that this is not the case here.

Element (%)	ALS Global results			May and Rumble, 2004		Cao et al, 2016		ALS detection limit
	Mean	1 SD	2 SD	Certified value	Error	Mean	1 SD	
Al	2.23	0.04	0.08	2.297	0.018	2.23	0.16	0.01
Ca	0.56	0.02	0.04	0.519	0.02	0.534	0.025	0.01
Fe	2.01	0.06	0.12	2.008	0.039	2.00	0.07	0.01
K	0.86	0.03	0.05	0.864	0.016	0.801	0.157	0.01
Mg	0.38	0.01	0.02	0.388	0.009	0.392	0.019	0.01
Mn	0.0232	0.0007	0.0014	0.02345	0.00028	0.0211	0.00019	0.0005
Na	0.74	0.02	0.04	0.741	0.017	0.774	0.0112	0.01
Ti	0.433	0.011	0.022	0.456	0.021	0.498	0.045	0.02

Table 1 Major element means and standard deviations from nine analyses by ALS Global Method ME-MS63r. Certified values and errors are from multiple INAA analyses (May & Rumble, 2004). Means and standard deviations (Cao et al., 2017) are from seven acid digestions followed by ICP-AES analysis.

Trace elements

Trace element concentrations are presented for elements that have a certified value (May & Rumble, 2004), are reported by Cao et al. (2017), or are commonly used in geochemical studies of sediment provenance (e.g. Totten et al. 2000; Cullers 2002; Alexander et al. 2025), but do not have either of these values reported (Table 2). Se was not included as it is below the detection limit for ALS Global Method ME-MS61r. The mean concentrations of Cu, As, and Cd are within 1 SD of the certified values. Zn, Pb, and Th are within 2 SD of the certified values, while Th is also within 1 SD of the concentration reported by Cao et al. (2017). The mean concentration of V is outside 2 SD of the certified value, but within 1 SD of the reported concentration (Cao et al., 2017).

For elements without a certified value, Ba is within 1 SD, and Sc, Co, and Cs are within 2 SD of concentrations reported by Cao et al. (2017). Rb and U are close to 2 SD, but Cao et al. (2017) report larger errors associated with their results for these elements. For elements where the only available data

are the non-certified values (May & Rumble, 2004), Li, Sr and Sb are within 1 SD, and Ni and Sn are within 2 SD of these values. This leaves P and Cr, which do not match well with either the certified values (May & Rumble, 2004) or the concentrations reported by Cao et al. (2017). For P, all reported errors were relatively large, and do overlap, but agreement between any of the reported means is not good. For Cr, the mean determined by ALS Global Method ME-MS63r is below the reported values, which are in good agreement with each other (Cao et al., 2017; May & Rumble, 2004). This likely results from both reporting INAA results, and suggests that an acid digestion did not completely dissolve all minerals containing Cr (Totland et al., 1992). Using a 95% confidence interval (2 SD), there is overlap between the data reported here and that of Cao et al. (2017), however Cr data from this method should be used with caution. Finally, results are reported here for Y, Zr, and Nb, but no certified values are provided by NIST, and no reported concentrations were discovered in the literature for comparison.

Element (ppm)	ALS Global results			May and Rumble, 2004		Cao et al, 2016		ALS detection limit
	Mean	1 SD	2 SD	Certified value	Error	Mean	1 SD	
Li	17.2	0.8	1.7	(18)				0.2
P	291	6	11	270	10	240	52	10
Sc	4.3	0.2	0.3	(5)		4.53*	0.06	0.1
V	41	1	2	44.84	0.76	40.4*	7.6	1
Cr	34	2	4	40.9	1.9	39.9*	2.2	1
Co	4.4	0.2	0.4	(5)		4.61	0.14	0.1
Ni	21.3	0.7	1.4	(23)				0.2
Cu	9.9	0.6	1.2	10.01	0.34			0.2
Zn	46	1	3	48.9	1.6			2
As	6.6	0.5	1.1	6.23	0.21	6.48	1.12	0.2
Rb	33.0	1.0	2.0	(38)		35.9	4.4	0.1
Sr	68.9	1.8	3.6	68				0.2
Y	8.4	0.4	0.7					0.1
Zr	66.6	2.6	5.1					0.5
Nb	10.4	0.3	0.6					0.1
Cd	0.14	0.01	0.02	0.148	0.007			0.02
Sn	1.3	0.1	0.3	(1)				0.2
Sb	0.31	0.04	0.08	(0.3)				0.05
Cs	1.27	0.05	0.10			1.18*	0.06	0.05
Ba	204	5	10	(210)		198	6	10
Pb	11.0	0.5	1.1	11.7	1.2			0.5
Th	5.42	0.40	0.80	(5.8)		5.55	0.52	0.01
U	1.6	0.1	0.1	(2)		1.77	0.04	0.1

Table 2 Trace element means and standard deviations from nine analyses by ALS method ME-MS63r. Certified values and errors are from multiple INAA repeats, and reported values are given in parentheses (May & Rumble, 2004). Means and standard deviations (Cao et al., 2017) are from seven acid digestions followed by ICP-AES and ICP-MS analysis, except those denoted by an asterisk* which are from INAA (4 sample repeats).

Rare earth elements

There are no certified values for the REE (May & Rumble, 2004), however concentrations measured by ICP-MS after acid digestion have been published by Cao et al. (2017) and these data are used here for comparison with ALS Global Method ME-MS63r (Table 3). Unlike the trace elements, a clear trend is visible in the data, with the agreement between the two datasets decreasing with increasing atomic mass (Figure 1). From La to Sm, the concentrations match very closely, well within the 1 SD range. From Eu on, the measured concentrations from ALS Global Method ME-MS63r begin to fall below those of Cao et al. (2017), with the difference increasing towards the heavier REE. Eu and Tb are still within 1 SD and Gd within 2 SD. For Dy, Tm, Yb and Lu, the error bars overlap (Figure 1).

Element (ppm)	ALS Global results			Cao et al, 2016		ALS detection limit
	Mean	1 SD	2 SD	Mean	1 SD	
La	18.3	0.9	1.7	18.1	0.9	0.005
Ce	39.6	1.8	3.6	39.1	2	0.01
Pr	4.45	0.17	0.34	4.49	0.21	0.03
Nd	17.1	0.7	1.4	17.2	0.8	0.1
Sm	3.2	0.2	0.4	3.21	0.12	0.03
Eu	0.54	0.03	0.07	0.566	0.014	0.03
Gd	2.42	0.18	0.37	2.75	0.19	0.05
Tb	0.33	0.03	0.05	0.357	0.011	0.01
Dy	1.76	0.12	0.23	2.02	0.07	0.05
Ho	0.32	0.02	0.04	0.376	0.013	0.01
Er	0.9	0.05	0.10	1.07	0.04	0.03
Tm	0.13	0.01	0.02	0.151	0.006	0.01
Yb	0.86	0.07	0.13	1.03	0.06	0.03
Lu	0.13	0.01	0.02	0.155	0.008	0.01

Table 3 REE means and standard deviations from nine analyses by ALS Global Method ME-MS63r. Means and standard deviations (Cao et al., 2017) are from seven acid digestions followed by ICP-MS analysis

Figure 1 Mean REE concentrations from nine analyses by ALS Global Method ME-MS63r (red), with error bars representing 2 SD (95% confidence) compared with published mean REE concentrations (black) from seven acid digestions followed by ICP-MS analysis (Cao et al., 2017), with error bars representing 1 SD (68% confidence).

Discussion

Overall, the results from ALS Global Method ME-MS61r for NIST Standard Reference Material® 1646a are in good agreement with the published concentrations for the majority of elements of interest (Cao et al., 2017; May & Rumble, 2004). Given that these samples were run at random intervals over a period of seven years, they are remarkably consistent. All major elements are within an acceptable range, along with most trace elements. While internally consistent over multiple analyses, concentrations of Ti and Cr are lower than reported values, possibly due to being present in refractory minerals such as rutile and chromite, which are resistant to acid digestion (Totland et al., 1992). The same may be true for Zr as zircon is refractory, but no published data are available for comparison.

The REE data are internally consistent over multiple analyses spanning seven years, however, there is a concerning disagreement between the ALS Global Method ME-MS61r and concentrations measured by Cao et al. (2017) that increases towards the heavy REE. Given that both methods use a similar acid digestion process, this would not be expected. Other authors have provided data for some REE in NIST Standard Reference Material® 1646a along with their research data. INAA results show consistently higher concentrations of REE (Cesar Wasserman et al., 2001; Saha et al., 2015), however this technique cannot be used for all REE. Similarly, measured concentrations are higher for ICP-MS analysis using a lithium metaborate fusion sample preparation instead of an acid digestion (Saha et al., 2015). This would

suggest that some REE in NIST Standard Reference Material® 1646a are present in minerals resistant to acid digestion (Totland et al., 1992). It is likely that the same is true for Y, but again no published data are available for comparison.

Conclusion

All these observations should be considered when using ALS Global Method ME-MS61r for geochemical research. In general, the data are internally consistent and robust when compared with published analyses. However, acid digestion may not completely dissolve resistant minerals (Totland et al., 1992), leading to erroneously low measurement of elements such as Ti, Cr, Zr, heavy REE and Y. When comparing research samples within a study, any relationships observed should be accurate. However, caution should be used when comparisons are made with other data sets, and when making provenance interpretations using standard geochemical plots that include these elements (e.g. Totten et al. 2000; Cullers 2002).

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Data availability statement

The individual sample analytical results on which this report is based are available in the supplementary spreadsheet, ALS_rock_standard_results.xlsx

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